

Aminolysis of 2,3-Cyclopenten-3',5'-diyl]-endo-N-(2'',4''-dinitrophenoxy)-succinimide with Morpholine, Piperidine, Pyrrolidine and Cyclohexylamine in Ethyl Acetate

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Mechanism of aromatic substitution reactions by amine nucleophiles in partially aqueous and in dipolar aprotic media seems to be well-established¹. According to Banjoko *et al.*² aminolysis with primary amines are both base-catalysed and non-catalysed whereas others indicate them to be wholly base-catalysed³. The broad mechanistic feature is given in Scheme 1. However, the mechanism through

Scheme 1

which base catalysis occurs in aromatic substitution reactions by amine nucleophiles in aprotic solvents in particular, is still a subject of discussion⁴. As substrates with sterically congested nucleofuges have not been investigated thoroughly so far, we have studied aminolysis reactions on the title compound with four different amines, viz. piperidine, morpholine, cyclohexylamine and pyrrolidine in ethyl acetate at 35° and results are presented here.

Results and Discussion

The results of the reactions of compound 1 in ethyl acetate with piperidine (PIP), morpholine (MOR), cyclohexylamine (CHA) and pyrrolidine (PYR) (Table 1) indicate base-catalysis with PYR and non-catalysis with all other amines. Plots of k_A vs [amine] are linear (Fig.1) with negligible slopes with all amines studied except with pyrrolidine where the plot is linear with slope ($k'' = 33.6 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and intercept ($k' = 3.6 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) characteristic of base catalysis. The value of k''/k' ($= 960 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$) also supports such a view.

The mechanism of the reaction may be interpreted from Scheme 2. The formation of the intermediate complex (I) is rate-determining⁵ in each case except for pyrrolidine. Apparently due to resonance, ethyl acetate acts more as a hydrogen bond acceptor than as a donor and easily forms a

heteroconjugate acid $\text{BH}^+ \cdots \text{S}$ (where B is pyrrolidine and S is ethyl acetate; either the carbonyl oxygen or the alkyl oxygen of ethyl acetate participates). Electrophilic catalysis⁶ by $\text{BH}^+ \cdots \text{S}$ assists in the expulsion of the nucleofuge. Jain *et al.*⁷ extended this mechanism to explain inverse temperature effect observed in aminolysis reactions of some *o*-aryloximes in hydrogen bond acceptor solvents.

Fig. 1. Plots of k_A vs [Amine] for the reactions of 2,3-[cyclopenten-3',5'-diyl]-endo-N-(2'',4''-dinitrophenoxy)succinimide with (Δ) morpholine, (□) piperidine, (☆) pyrrolidine and (○) cyclohexylamine in ethyl acetate at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The results (Table 1) show that the reaction with pyrrolidine is most facile towards the substrate compared to other amines used. The second order rate constants increase linearly with [PYR]. Further, the following order of reactivity of nucleophiles is observed: $\text{PYR} > \text{PIP} > \text{MOR} > \text{CHA}$. A combination of base strength, molecular size and shape of amine used explains the observed order. A difference in reactivity between pyrrolidine ($\text{p}K_a$ in water 11.12) and piperidine ($\text{p}K_a$ in water 11.22) may be interpreted in terms of their conformational stabilities. In the

Scheme 2

case of piperidinolysis a clear isosbestic point at 310 nm was observed indicating absence of any stable intermediate in the reaction. In pyrrolidinolysis, no such isosbestic point was observed.

TABLE I—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_A) FOR THE REACTIONS OF 1 WITH DIFFERENT NUCLEOPHILES IN ETHYL ACETATE

[Substrate] = 4.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, temp. = $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Nucleophile	10^{-4} [Nu] mol dm ⁻³	$10^{-1} k_A$ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹ dm ³
Cyclohexylamine	29.5	0.33
	44.3	0.31
	59.0	0.41
	73.8	0.40
	88.5	0.39
Morpholine	13.0	3.02
	16.5	2.90
	19.5	3.04
	26.5	2.94
	38.5	3.04
Piperidine	5.0	32.6
	5.5	32.6
	6.0	32.7
	7.8	32.7
	8.2	32.4
Pyrrolidine	0.8	56.0
	1.0	73.0
	1.5	87.7
	1.8	108.6
	2.4	119.7

Pyrrolidine has a puckered ring similar to cyclopentane

and undergoes pseudo-rotation among the various half-chair and envelope forms. Piperidine exists in the chair conformation in which the hydrogen of the NH group occupies an axial position and to meet the spatial requirements of the lone-pair electrons which comfortably occupies the equatorial position. The difference in behaviour and reactivity may arise from steric interactions⁸ forced by differences in conformation between the amine moieties in the intermediate σ -adduct as they release the nucleofuge. The smaller size of pyrrolidine and its heteroconjugate acid also plays a crucial role.

Experimental

The preparation of compound 1 from *N*-hydroxy derivative of cyclopentadiene maleic anhydride adduct 2 is described elsewhere¹: 1, m.p. 210–12°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1750 (C=O), 1350, 1525 (C–NO₂), 1600 cm⁻¹ (N–O); λ_{\max} (CH₃CN) 247 (log ϵ = 4.01); δ (CDCl₃) 1.3 (2H, m), 3.4 (4H, m), 6.3 (2H, m), 7.1–8.5 (3H, m, trisubstituted aromatic).

The reactions were studied with morpholine, piperidine, pyrrolidine and cyclohexylamine in ethyl acetate using five different amine concentrations under pseudo-first order conditions at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. All the reactions were studied at the λ_{\max} of the corresponding coloured aminolysis product using a Shimadzu UV-2100 spectrophotometer. The solution of amine was placed in a quartz cuvette in a thermostatted cell compartment. The substrate solution was then injected into it and the absorbance recorded. The in-

finite reading was recorded after ten half-lines.

The products *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)amine (3) and the parent compound (2) were characterised by direct comparison of electronic spectra, R_f values and m.p. of the corresponding authentic sample.

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